

EVALUATING QUALITY OF LIFE INDICATORS IN INDIVIDUALS AFFECTED BY SYPHILIS

Utayev Akbar Jurakulovich

Chief physician of the Samarkand regional branch of the Republican Specialized Dermatovenerological and Cosmetology Scientific and Practical Medical Center

Nazarov Jamshid Abdurashidovich

Assistant at the Department of Skin and Venereal Diseases, Samarkand State Medical University

Toshev Suhrob Uktamjon ugli

Assistant at the Department of Skin and Venereal Diseases, Samarkand State Medical University

Annotation: this article attempts to reveal the main reasons for assessing the quality of life indicators in patients with syphilis in dynamics. To carry out scientific work, the author carried out the object of the study was 250 patients aged 16–67 years (mean age 23.4 ± 3.9 years) with established diagnoses A51 "Early syphilis", A52 "Late syphilis", A53 "Other and unspecified forms of syphilis".

The problem in question is still little studied, therefore, requires more thorough research.

Key words: Syphilis, quality of life of patients.

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqola dinamikada sifilisli bemorlarning hayot sifati ko'rsatkichlarini baholashning asosiy sabablarini ochib berishga harakat qiladi. Ilmiy ishlarni amalga oshirish uchun muallif amalga oshirdi tadqiqot ob'ekti 16-67 yoshdagi (o'rtacha yoshi $23,4 \pm 3,9$ yosh) 250 nafar bemor A51 "Erta sifilis", A52 "Kechki sifilis", A53 "Sifilisning boshqa va aniqlanmagan shakllari" tashxisi bilan aniqlandi.

Ko'rib chiqilayotgan muammo hali ham kam o'rganilgan, shuning uchun chuqurroq tadqiqotni talab qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Sifilis, bemorlarning hayot sifati.

Аннотация: в данной статье предпринята попытка раскрыть основные причины оценки показателей качества жизни больных сифилисом в динамике. Для выполнения научной работы автор осуществил Объектом

исследования стали 250 больных в возрасте 16–67 лет (средний возраст $23,4 \pm 3,9$ года) с установленными диагнозами А51 «Ранний сифилис», А52 «Поздний сифилис», А53 «Другие и неуточненные формы сифилиса».

Рассматриваемая проблема еще мало изучена, поэтому требует более тщательного исследования.

Ключевые слова: Сифилис, качество жизни больных.

Introduction: Syphilis (outdated: lues from lat. Lues - infection) is a systemic venereal infectious disease affecting the skin, mucous membranes, internal organs, bones, nervous system with a successive change in the stages of the disease, caused by bacteria of the species *Treponema pallidum* (*pallidum* subspecies *pallidum*, belonging to the genus *Treponema* (*Treponema*) of the order Spirochaetes (Spirochaetales). The prognosis of the disease in most cases is favorable. Timely diagnosis and adequate treatment leads to a complete recovery. However, with a long-term chronic course and in cases of infection of the fetus in the womb, persistent irreversible changes develop, leading to disability.

Aim: to assess the dynamics of the quality of life of patients with syphilis.

Materials and methods: the object of the study was 250 patients aged 16–67 years (mean age 23.4 ± 3.9 years) with established diagnoses А51 "Early syphilis", А52 "Late syphilis", А53 "Other and unspecified forms of syphilis. To assess the quality of life indicators, a validated SF-36 questionnaire was used, using which patients were tested before treatment, 1 month and 3 months after the end of treatment. The study was conducted on the basis of the Orenburg Regional Clinical Dermatovenerological Dispensary. The questionnaire consists of 36 questions grouped into 8 scales. The data obtained were compared with the results of the reference database of population values of the standardized indicators of the questionnaire for residents of the Russian Federation. The calculation of the integral scales of the questionnaire was carried out according to the methodological recommendations developed by the Preference Company.

Results: in patients with primary syphilis, there was a decrease in the level of quality of life with a predominance of influence on the physical component of health (general health scale) before treatment (decrease to 56.8 - by 12.6%) and after 1 month (decrease to 59.8 -8%), and after 3 months - indicators of quality of life became close to the reference values (65). The greatest decrease was noted in the psychological component of health (on the scales of role activity, general health, vital activity, social functioning, emotional state) before the start of treatment for secondary syphilis (decrease to 49.8-17%), latent early (decrease to 55.2 -8% and late (decrease to 52 - by 13.4%) After 1 month, normalization is noted only with latent early syphilis (up to 59.5), after 3 months - there is a tendency to normalize indicators (up to 57) with latent syphilis late, although the average values for the population were not achieved. During the observation period in the secondary form of nosology, the indicators did not reach the reference indicators. The study showed a slight effect of the disease on the quality of life in latent syphilis, unspecified, both before treatment and after 1 and 3 months from the moment observations.

Conclusions: the study showed the heterogeneity of the impact of this disease on the indicators of the quality of life of patients, while there is a dynamics in their change depending on the stage of the disease, which must be taken into account as an important component for a full psycho-social and physical adaptation after treatment.

Literature:

1. Abdullaev X. D. et al. EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE DRUG GEAPON IN THE TREATMENT OF GENITAL CANDYLOMAS //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 02. – С. 16-19.
2. Абдуллаев Х. Д. и др. Определение цитокинового статуса у больных с псориазом на фоне стандартного лечения //Общество и инновации. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 1/S. – С. 625-629.

3. Ахмедова М. М., Абдуллаев Х. Д., Камолова М. И. ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ МЕТОДОВ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ОНИХОМИКОЗОВ У ВЗРОСЛЫХ //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 186-190.
4. Тошев С. У., Аширов З. Ф., Абдуллаев Х. Д. ЛЕЧЕНИЕ ВИТИЛИГО 308-нм ЭКСИМЕРНЫМ ЛАЗЕРОМ //Актуальные аспекты медицинской деятельности. – 2021. – С. 240-243.
5. Davlatovich A. X., Haydarjonovna X. S., Raximjon N. S. JYBYK BILAN BO'LGAN PROSTATITNI DAVOLASH USULINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 359-361.
6. Ахмедова М., Расулова Н., Абдуллаев Х. Изучение парциальных функций почек у детей раннего возраста с нефропатией обменного генеза //Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины. – 2016. – №. 2 (87). – С. 37-40.
7. Нарзикулов Р. и др. Принципы терапии у женщин больных гонореей ассоциированные иппп //Журнал вестник врача. – 2019. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 99-102.
8. Нуруллаева А. А., Рахматова А. Х., Абдуллаев Х. Д. ЗНАЧЕНИЕ МИКРОБНОГО ОБСЕМЕНЕНИЯ КОЖИ ПРИ НЕКОТОРЫХ ЗУДЯЩИХ ДЕРМАТОЗАХ //Молодежь и медицинская наука в XXI веке. – 2019. – С. 125-125.
9. Abdullaev X. D. et al. EXPERIENCE OF USING THE DRUG GEON IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS FOCAL SCLERODERMA //ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 03. – С. 60-63.
10. Абдуллаев Х. Д., Собиров М. С., Жумаева Д. Х. НЕРВНО-ПСИХИЧЕСКИЙ СТАТУС У БОЛЬНЫХ СЕБОРЕЕЙ //Молодежь и медицинская наука в XXI веке. – 2018. – С. 115-116.

- 11.Ахмедов Ш. К. и др. ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ИЗОТРЕТИНОИНА ПРИ ЛЕЧЕНИИ УГРЕВОЙ БОЛЕЗНИ //Академический журнал Западной Сибири. – 2015. – Т. 11. – №. 1. – С. 56-56.
- 12.Абдуллаев Х., Толибов М. Allergodermatozlar bilan bog'liq bo'lgan vulgar aspeni kompleks davolash Samaraligini o'rganish //Журнал гепатогастроэнтерологических исследований. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 3.2. – С. 73-74.
- 13.Davlatovich A. X., O'gli A. B. X., O'gli I. A. S. BOLALARDA GENITAL GERPESNI DAVOLASH SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 367-369.
- 14.Абдуллаев Х. Д. и др. ЛАЗЕР В ЛЕЧЕНИИ ВИТИЛИГО //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 495-500.
- 15.Xolmurodovich D. J., Umidovich N. T., Davlatovich A. X. CLINIC COURSE OF NONSPECIFIC PNEUMONIA //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 510-513.
- 16.Davlatovich A. X. et al. USING IMMUNOMAX AND 0.1% TACROLIMUS OINTMENT IN THE TREATMENT OF VITILIGO //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 559-562.
- 17.Toshev S. U. APPLICATIONS OF ELACON FOR LICHEN PLANE //Asian journal of pharmaceutical and biological research. – 2022. – Т. 11. – №. 2.
- 18.Hikmatovich I. N. et al. Local Treatment of Children with Atopic Dermatitis //International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 235-237.
- 19.Uktamovich T. S., Umedovich S. U. Effectiveness of Treatment of Testicular Torsion //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 647-649.

- 20.Uktamovich T. S., Fakhriddinovich F. K. Effectiveness of the Treatment of Limited Scleroderma //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 5. – С. 650-652.